

Study and development of innovative Machine Learning techniques for reliability test systems

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1 Introduction

An implementation of an analytical approach on reliability test systems for electronic components is introduced. The work presents an integrated solution, merging a deeper understanding of the process through AI algorithms, knowledge extraction from raw data by Data Mining and real-time control due to data collection by sensors – directly from the stress process.

2 Aim

Given the increasingly massive use of electronics in applications that also pervade our daily life, it becomes critical to ensure the safety and reliability of electronic components. Consequently, testing machines for electronic components also need to be as reliable and fault-free as possible. To the aim, new algorithms have been designed and implemented to model the components of test machines, capable of receiving without conflicts the information coming from heterogeneous hardware and field sensors.

3 Materials and Methods

A Digital Twin has been created to model the behavior of the test machine in an integrated way. It can realize the following functions: - monitoring and optimization of the use of the test machine, through a model that allows the classification of ordinary and abnormal operating conditions - modulation of KPIs for scheduled maintenance, according to the actual use of the machine, based on real-time information on the

status of each of its components predictive maintenance, integrated with preventive maintenance and ordinary system management, to predict failures based on the operating trends of the components and the processes, thus providing an analytical tool to anticipate maintenance interventions.

4 Results

Better monitoring of operations, with higher availability and OEE, was achieved when compared to traditional process control. The model developed helps to determine the useful life of the most significant and critical components of the machine and simplifies the knowledge of the process phases and the identification of the most critical sub-processes. It also helps to test the most appropriate actions on the DT, significantly reducing the risks of service interruption on the machines in production.

5 Conclusions

The proposed work constitutes a flexible, scalable and inter operable solution that helps to understand in advance when components or processes are drifting, proceeding with the most appropriate maintenance or replacement actions.

6 Key Words

Predictive Maintenance, Reliability Test, Digital Twin, Machine Learning, Data Mining, OEE.